

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

MODELLING PROPOSED SDN PARALLEL TOPOLOGY AND EVALUATION OF ITS RELIABILITY

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Abstract

This paper presents a solution for enhancing the defense level of the software-defined network (SDN) structure, by proposing another topology for SDN controllers called the parallel topology. In this topology, the controllers interact in a parallel way with each other and work as a single controller like one brain. This solution could be a way to enhance the reliability of the SDN environment to defend against some cyber threats mostly DoS/DDoS threats. This paper depicts the modeling of this topology using the Petri Nets system and then compares it with the modeling of the Ordinary topology, which is the already existing topology that has merely a single controlling point.

Keywords: East-westbound API, Generalized Stochastic Petri Nets, hydra, Ordinary topology, Parallel topology, RSA, virtual private network.

1. Introduction

Previously we have described the software-defined network structure and how it works [1 - 3]. It mainly comprises new way of managing the computer network to facilitate network management. This is done by extracting the control ability from the network devices, rendering them merely packets forwarding devices. While the control will be a dedicated virtual plane represented by the controller that can be of a software or a hardware nature, and labeled as the control plane. Meanwhile the switches which became merely packets forwarding devices will be labeled as the forwarding plane or layer. The ability to develop applications that will manage the control plane will lead to the emergence of the application layer, those applications will be designed as per the needs of the enterprise or system administrator.

All the above will facilitate the network management by creating a single point of management and policy enforcement over the whole network's structure and that is one of the advantages of the software-defined networks.

But, despite that this feature which is the single point of management; is a strength point in the structure of SDN it could be a vulnerability as well since it could be used as a Single Point Of Failure weakness point or in short (SPOF), in order to solve that, some SDN environments could use multiple controllers. In our research, we use multiple controllers in different ways and those ways or topologies differ from each other in the way their SDN controllers interact between each other.

There have been three main SDN controllers' *topologies* proposed to patch the aforementioned issues, those topologies could use multiple controllers to assure the security of SDN and overcome the (SPOF) issue and they are:

- Serial topology: which we have discussed in an earlier article [4].

- Parallel topology: which will be discussed in this article.

- Hybrid topology: which consists of 6 controllers working together and combining the features of both the previous topologies [5].

Alongside with those proposed topologies, there will be a suite of suggested algorithms that will work as a framework on top of the controllers in the aforementioned topologies. These algorithms are:

1.1. The hydra framework Hydra is the result of the later mentioned algorithms added to them some counter measurements against some cyber-attacks like the DoS/DDoS [6]. An example of these measurements could be installing botnets [7] within the network nodes to deter any kind of DoS/DDoS [8] attack by attacking the attacker's IP address. The composition of these methodologies and others would give the SDN controllers' topology flexibility and ability to behave like the hydra microscopic creature; if you cut one head another one grows, the same thing here with those algorithms to secure the controllers and the connection between them, that will make the topologies more capable of handling threats and in case of an attack on one of the controllers another one will be elected as the main one like in serial or hybrid topology or the controllers will deal with the attacker and continue managing the network to bridge the gap in case of the parallel topology.

1.2. VPN is an abbreviation for (Virtual Private Network), the VPN can be leveraged to secure the channel of connection or the east-westbound API [9] between the multiple controllers and that by leveraging the internet protocol security (IPsec) technique that is included in VPN. The VPN technologies can provide certainty of sensitive data confidentiality to be kept transmitted on the network so that only authorized users are able to access sensitive data [10]. Two controllers could be connected together by leveraging the VPN's channel regardless of their location and proximity, and they could securely exchange the information and that

provides better security against cyber-attacks; man in the middle (MITM) attack is considered as an example of those cyber-attacks [11]

1.3. Double RSA the algorithm of RSA stands for Rivest–Shamir–Adleman (RSA) which are the initials of family names of its inventors. RSA is a well-established public-key crypto algorithm. It is in use for securing data transmission on a wide range. This encryption methodology comprises mainly a public key for encryption which has to be different from the key used for decryption which will be secretly kept (private). It is worth mentioning that Clifford Cocks, which was an English mathematician who worked for the British intelligence agency Government Communications Headquarters (GCHQ), was responsible for developing a system in 1973, and that was not declassified until 1997. Public Key Cryptography (PKC) works on the concept of dual keys [12]. The RSA encryption shall be used here as well. The implantation of this algorithm in the proposed framework will be differently conducted. The including will be done by starting two channels meaning, there will be a double ciphering channel. In other words, rather than using one public encryption key and two different private keys in each ciphering and deciphering operation; two distinct keys that are public will be leveraged with other four different keys that will be considered private keys. Each communication node will have its own set of keys that will help in starting a channel of secure communication for sending data and another channel of communication for receiving data.

1.4. Blockchain is one of the most soaring up technologies nowadays due to one of its main participations, which is the cryptocurrency technology. This technology is also merged with the Hydra framework but in another way than the way used in cryptocurrency. It is also used in some other fields like in networks but in a different way like in the Marconi protocol [13]. Blockchain here will be used in another way to develop a secure channel for exchanging configuration updates between controllers.

2. Materials used

This article talks about a proposed topology to enhance the security of software-defined networks, which is the parallel topology. This topology is going to be modelled and to get results; a software tool was used. This tool is called PIPE which is based on Markov chain and implements petri nets system and using the generalized stochastic petri nets (GSPN) in it to figure out the durability and feasibility of the topology and whether it's better than the other previously suggested topologies or not. Then this paper compares the Parallel topology with the Ordinary topology. GSPN is a module of six tuples (P, T, F, W, M₀, and λ) where:

- P= {P₁, P₂... P_m} represents a set of finite nature of places, where n ≥ 0.
- T= T₁ ∪ T₂, T₁= {t₁, t₂... t_m} represents a set of finite nature of timed transitions, and every transition is correlated with a random time of delay between the functions of enabling and firing. Also, T₂= {t_{m+1}, t_{m+2}... t_n} represents the set of immediate transitions of a finite nature. It is possible to fire these transitions randomly. In addition, the delay time will be zero.

- While F can be described mathematically as $F \subseteq (PxT) \cap (TxP)$, which is an arc set.

- W refers to the weight arcs operation, so: $F \lambda \{1, 2, 3 \dots\}$.

- In addition, M₀: P à {0, 1, 2, 3 ...} represents the initial marking, that can be described as $(PxT) = \emptyset \cap (TxP) = \emptyset$.

- Last but not least, λ= {λ₁, λ₂, λ₃ ... λ_n} describes firing rates group or category referring to timed transitions. Where every single rate represents the transition's average firing times per unit of time [14].

2.1. Parallel topology

This article concentrates on the parallel topology and compare it with the ordinary topology, which is an already existing topology that encompasses mainly one controller representing the control plane of the whole structure. In the Parallel topology, there will be three controllers working and interacting together as a completely one entity integrated together where the info is processed synchronously. Each controller will deal with any area or segment of the network especially, if it was closer to this slice or segment than other controllers were. Meaning that, each controller will give higher priority to closer network segments than the further or more distant segments (of course the distance will be calculated based on the number of hops in the path between the network slice and the controller), of course the updates will be also every 10 seconds. We call this topology as the parallel topology since all controllers work together in parallel so, there is no priority numbers here because they all behave like parts of one main controller where each one of its nodes will serve the closest switches to it first so, the priority for a switch in France to be served by a controller in France will be higher than that of a switch in Russia based on the number of hops between the switch and the controller. As shown in the figure 1.

Which means that, if we have three controllers connected in a parallel topology and they're distributed in France, Moldova and Russia respectively then; the part or node of the that big main controller that lies in Moldova will serve the switches lying in Moldova for speed reasons. The other switches lying in Russia and France will be served by the controllers of their own countries. In case if the controllers of their countries were busy and the Moldovan node was free then, it will automatically serve the Russian and French switches because all controllers are integrated with each other in a parallel way so, they behave as one distributed controller over those countries. Despite that the controllers here work simultaneously like one and share the same database of configuration but, the updates will be also every 10 seconds but they will be mere acknowledgements.

In some cyber-threat situations like DoS/DDoS attack situation, it is possible to have working controllers fill the place of the infected controller and try to deal with the coming flooding requests and here we will have one of two cases:

- The infected controller will be isolated using access control lists or any other technology. And others

will keep working like before like one controlling entity containing the rest of controllers.

- On the other hand, the two other controllers will try to ease the pressure off of the infected controller by taking a huge load of the requests coming from the attacking source to prevent the attacked controller from

being down completely. Until the attack source gets blocked and counter attacked; or if that fails and the other 2 controllers behave slowly or respond too late then, they will attack the attacking source with a counter DoS/DDoS attack and then they'll block both the attacker's IP and the infected controller's as well and we'll go back to step 1.

Figure 1. Structure of the Parallel Topology.

2.2. Ordinary topology

Which is a simple topology representing software-defined networks. This topology contains a one controlling point responsible for managing the entire network's topology. It manages the switches through the openflow protocol. The switches in return deal with the clients' requests.

The controller could stop if it was submerged with many pseudo requests when conducting cyber-attacks like DoS/DDoS attacks. If there's no substitute for the controller, the whole network could be in danger in case the controller was disrupted or if the switches got hacked via the single controlling point. The figure 2 depicts single-controller SDN structure or as it's called here, the Ordinary topology.

Figure 2. Structure of the Ordinary Topology.

2.3. Modelling using Petri Nets system

Petri networks were developed for depicting chemical processes. Petri nets methodology offers a notation on a graphical basis for step-based procedural systems like concurrent execution systems and iteration procedures. This technique has a mathematical description. The theoretic aspect of Petri nets allows precise modeling and analysis of system behavior [15]. This paper depicts the usage of petri nets to model the Parallel SDN controllers' topology to acquire an improved limitations comprehension of the topology, its capabilities, and also to extrapolate a mathematical definition

or an equation from its model's behavior. That equation can be used later for assessment of network's security risk mathematically.

3. Parallel controller modeling

3.1. Parallel Topology

The Parallel structure of network contains three main controllers that work together simultaneously as one entity like one brain. Those controllers send updates to each other of network configuration information about network nodes. The figure 3 shows the modelling of the parallel topology's structure using Petri Nets methodology.

Figure 3. Modeling of Parallel topology via GSPN module.

Parallel topology's scheme Explanation:

- Just like the Serial topology, the parallel topology will have three main controllers. Those proposed topologies differ between each other in the interactive behavior of their controlling nodes.

- Those three main controllers will interact with each other forming a whole controlling entity like one brain of three nodes. Those controlling points work simultaneously to deal with switches' requests.

- The controllers will work and collaborate in managing the network topology like one main controller.

- Every controller is going to serve network switches based on priority that will be determined based on the closest switches to it. The closest switches will be determined based on the number of hops.

- Every controller will exchange the configuration updates with the other remaining servers/controllers through a broadcast update every 10 seconds as well.

- Every 10 seconds the information of network configuration will be gathered meaning; every 10 seconds the three controlling nodes have the ability to update their network's general table status. The justification for that is that the three nodes; which form one triple-node controlling brain is going to exchange the info among each other every 10 seconds.

- If any of the controlling nodes is under attack, the remaining two controlling nodes will compensate for the absence of the infected node.

- All the network switches are already in connection with the three controllers. In case if there was a threat then, the framework will activate a bot and send it to the perpetrator's address. Then the jeopardized controlling node is going to be insulated; alongside the perpetrator. All forwarding data plane nodes, which are being served by the infected controller; will be served instantly by the other controllers. Table 1 describes the places.

Table 1

Places Description	
Place	Description
P5/P9/P1	Allocating the servers
P2/P10/P6	Active processing in the 1 st , 2 nd and 3 rd servers
P12-P17	Exchanging info between network controllers
P3/P7/P11	Controller restoring
P19/P20/P18	Attack on Controller/ Server
P8/ P0/P4	Moving back to first working status of the network before the attack

The table 2 below states the description of transitions.

Table 2

Transitions Description	
Transition	Description
T21/T23/T25	Server No.1,2 and 3 represent processing of requests
T9-T20	Servers Exchange configuration updates between each other
/T5/ T3/T4	Going back to the processing situation
T8/T6/T7/	State of attack on the server or controller
T22/ T26/T24/	Restoration of controller
T2/ T0/T1/	Returning to the original working status

3.2. Ordinary Topology

From figure 4, it is possible to notice that this modelling depicts the single-controller ordinary topology and shows its vulnerabilities.

Ordinary topology's scheme Explanation:

- The modelling of this topology depicts the already-existing, known model that leverages a single controlling node.

- The modelling of this topology was needed for the purpose of comparison to depict the effectiveness difference between the proposed topology and this topology.

- This scheme clarifies how a single controller can be vulnerable and ineffective against attacks due to the existence of (SPOF) which requires patching.

- The model here contains one controller to manage the whole network in a normal way until an attack takes place.

- If an attack occurs, the previous design proves that an attack is capable of disrupting the controller and every node connected to it. Therefore, the network model will be in danger in case of a successful attack on the controller, which states that the fault tolerance of this topology is zero.

Figure 4. Modelling of Ordinary topology via GSPN module.

Table number 3 explains places of the scheme.

Table 3

Place	Explanation
P1/P2/P0	Selecting process of switches
P3	Represents the key controlling
P4	Active state of requests processing
P6	Dealing with the new update / returning to original status
P7	Exchanging configuration updates
P5	Status of cyber-threat on the controlling node

Transitions are shown in table 4.

Table 4

Transition	Explanation
T1/ T0/T2	Controlling node receiving requests
T3	Active state of requests processing
T9	Status of treating requests
T8/T6/T7	Managing switches and dealing with them
T10	Cyber-threat state

3.3. Equation of Defense Factor (DF)

- **PIPE software's module of GSPN**

Now by comparing the two topologies based on the density of tokens in places that depict the controlling nodes in the SDN structure. In those places; tokens simulate the tasks performed and broadcasted every 10 seconds by the controllers, and of course the less busy the controller is; the better; due to the fact that it proves that SDN structure has a higher capability of deterring cyber-attacks especially DoS/DDoS. This comparison comprises value ω , which is the immediate transitions' weight which was left as default. Value (r) stands for timed transitions rate that was set to value of 0.1 because it is needed to broadcast those network updates/

configurations every 10 seconds; meaning that the state of the model will change every 10 seconds. It is possible to see the connection between rate and weight values:

- $\tau = 1/r$ (1)

- τ Means value of time, the value r refers to timed transitions density or rate. So, in case of a need set 10 seconds as value of time; that would mean that the rate value should be equal to 0.1.

- The transitions value is fixed; in each model; the value was set to 20 firings. Conducting the simulation with this value of firings, we get the numerical data as shown in table 5.

Table 5

The density of tokens in places behaving as controllers in SDN		
Places/ k_i	Algorithms	Structure/ Z_{k_i}
	P3	1.99975 \approx 2
	P1	0
	P5	0
	P9	0

The table 5 shows that by leveraging the parallel network structure or topology; the requests that the controllers deal with per time unit; will decrease in comparison with those data requests that are being handled via a single controlling node in the Ordinary SDN structure. This would show the SDN structure’s effectiveness in comparison to the Ordinary topology.

• **Defense Factor formula elaboration**

From the previous table we can see that SDN Parallel model can be more reliable because its controllers are mostly empty during the firings period. This means that the network that uses this topology will be having less occupied controllers hence, less DoS/DDoS attacks prone controllers because they will be more capable of dealing with requests.

So, using a module of PIPE software named as Generalized Stochastic Petri Nets (GSPN). GSPN is incorporated; within the PIPE, software can help in figuring out the results mentioned earlier. The gained data can be leveraged; in the equation that we suggest. This equation was made by observations based on various firings. This equation could be leveraged for assessment of SDN level of security in terms of cyberattacks especially those attacks that can exploit the busyness of controllers and use them for their advantage including the Denial of Service and Distributed Denial of Service threats; and that suggested formula is named as Defense Factor of Computer Networks. It is necessary to explain the basics on which the equation was formulated and the reasons of its formulation. This formula is derived to assess the effect of cyber-threats especially DoS/DDoS threats because of the key characteristic it has. This characteristic is the amount of requests being dealt with via network controlling node per unit of time. As mentioned earlier DoS/DDoS, attacks comprise submerging the intended attack point with pseudo requests in gigantic amounts, in order to disrupt or disable it completely. So, it should be known that the less occupied server/controller the better it is; since it will gain better ability in dealing with those requests; meaning a higher deterrence ability and a bigger response period. Therefore, this equation emphasizes the idea that states whenever the amount of requests is reduced the higher the security of the controllers will be. It is worth mentioning that this scientific work concentrates on increasing the networks security in the overall perspective, especially SDN. The controller is the core of the targeted SDN structure that needs to be protected and needs its level of security to be estimated, so that’s why it is critically important to incorporate this component with the equation in order for its security level assessment hence, determining the network’s security level.

$$\text{Let } DF=f \{K, Z\}, \tag{2}$$

K is a symbol for controllers’ quantity, while Z refers to how many requests are handled at a given time unit. Using the previous equation alongside Petri Nets elaborated models; gives a relationship that connects all of them and that is elaborated equation. Computer network requests in PN system are represented; by the amount of tokens occupying places that refer to control plane nodes.

Mathematical description of proposed Defense Factor formula is as the follows:

$$DF= \sum_i^n K_i \cdot \frac{1}{\sum_0^\infty Z_{k_i}}, \tag{3}$$

where DF represents Defense Factor of SDN ability to defend itself against cyber-threats, DF is equal to the summation of K_i , which refers to PN places quantity / control plane nodes, where $K_i=(K_1, K_2... K_n)$ and that summation is multiplied by 1 divided by Z_{k_i} which refers to the tokens’ density /requests in those places $K_i, Z_{k_i}=(0... \infty)$.

Because the more controllers SDN structure has; the better defense capability the network has against the DoS/DDoS attacks while the more requests the structure has; the less deterrence the SDN has hence, we can say that K_i should be directly proportional to DF in the formula while Z_{k_i} should be inversely proportional to the value of DF .

$$\text{Let } A = \frac{1}{\sum_{z=0}^\infty Z_{k_i}} \tag{4}$$

$$A= \tag{5}$$

Now if we implement the numerical data gained from simulation in this equation; we get the following Ordinary topology’s DF value:

$DFO = K_{O_i} \cdot 1/Z_{O_i} = 1 \times (1/T_{P3})$ à knowing that T_{P3} is the total average number of tokens in place number 3 that represents the main controller, that means:

$$DFO=1 \times 1/1.99975 = 0.50$$

DF of suggested Parallel structure will be as follows:

$DFP= K_{P_i} \cdot 1/Z_{P_i} = 3 \times (1/T_{P1+T_{P5}+T_{P9}})$ à where T_{P1}, T_{P5}, T_{P9} refer to the tokens’ density in those places 1, 5 and 9 respectively. These places represent the three main controllers in the SDN parallel structure, and this would mean:

$$DFP=3 \times 1/0 = \infty \approx \text{optimal è theoretically}$$

In conclusion, it is possible to notice here, that the Parallel structure represents a better quality in terms of security as compared to the Ordinary single-controller SDN model. In terms of DF , it is possible to compare the two SDN models as shown in Table 6.

Parallel and Ordinary SDN models in term of their DF values

Algorithm	Parallel Model	Ordinary Model
Defense factor DF	$\approx \infty$	0.50

4. Conclusions

The paper here, concentrates on increasing the software-defined network’s protection hence, turning SDN into a more protected environment, leading to protecting networks generally if those networks leverage the SDN structure.

This paper explains briefly, the previously proposed algorithms in the research. Those algorithms work together as a whole suite called the Hydra framework that will be used by the software-defined controllers to give them a better security and reliability in managing the network.

The presented Hydra framework is optional to be leveraged by the suggested topologies to solve issue of Single Point of Failure (SPOF) that serves as a positivity and an issue at the same time, due to its ability to facilitate the network management and at the same time can raise some security threats; since it promotes a single point of failure (SPOF).

This article gives an explanation about Parallel SDN model which is one of the three proposed topologies by the research.

The paper here gives a modelling approach for the Parallel model via the system of Petri Nets (PN) to

extrapolate a relationship which is used for mapping the level of cyber-threats in networking environment that leverage anyone of the suggested SDN structures.

This article compared between data received from the usage of GSPN module for Ordinary and Parallel topologies to see the effect of using parallel topology and then apply the results on the defense factor formula to see the mathematical and theoretical reliability of the newly proposed topology and its advantages over the Ordinary topology.

The results gained by using the defense factor formula were promising and show a great overall enhancement on the performance of the SDN paradigm when dealing with requests.

The gained defense factor (DF) value of Parallel SDN model was infinity which is merely a theoretical and mathematical result showing that the average tokens’ number in controlling places / SDN control plane nodes; was zero most of the elapsed operation time.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

Annex 1. Simulation process of Petri Nets Model of Parallel Topology.

Annex 2. Table showing the Average number of tokens (network requests) on a place (main controller) for the Parallel topology.

Average Number of Tokens on a Place

Place Number of Tokens	
P0	0.23658
P1	0
P10	0.10948
P11	0.78103
P12	0.32674
P13	0.32664
P14	0
P15	0.32669
P16	0.32663
P17	0.32674
P18	0.1093
P19	0.10933
P2	0.1093
P20	0.10948
P3	0.78139
P4	0.23664
P5	0
P6	0.10933
P7	0.78134
P8	0.23711
P9	0

Annex 3. Simulation process of Petri Nets Model of Ordinary Topology.

Annex 4. Table showing the Average number of tokens (network requests) on a place (main controller) for the Ordinary topology.

Average Number of Tokens on a Place

Place Number of Tokens

P0	0
P1	0
P2	0
P3	2
P4	0
P5	1
P6	0
P7	0

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